

1 **The androgen and estrogen receptor are silenced in the cervix during progression from CIN2/3 to**
2 **cervical carcinoma.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We studied total transcription in the cervix during transformation in vivo in humans. The role of estrogen
8 and androgens in breast and prostate cancer is more widely understood than in the cervix. We discovered
9 that silencing of androgen and estrogen receptors was likely a requisite transcriptional event during
10 progression from CIN2/3 to carcinoma. The data allude to a cervix-specific hormone receptor event during
11 progression to transformation but do not disclude the existence of a transcriptional event involving the
12 estrogen receptor that occurs during transformation in all cells.
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